

Details of the dataset

The data and scripts are openly available. If you would like to use a dataset in a publication, then please acknowledge the source of the data by citing the manuscript. Please also contact the corresponding author to ensure that we are not planning similar analyses. We are also happy to share raw EEG data and to help with questions concerning the data, please contact the corresponding authors (Malte.Kobelt@rub.de).

Data

Provided data includes preprocessed trial-level EEG data and electrodes positions in MNI space of each participant. The provided data thereby enables to conduct all statistical tests, to generate all presented figures and to follow all analysis steps after preprocessing.

01preprocessing\ref_clean_induced

Contains preprocessed EEG data of each participant to run all analyses.

data.trialinfo

Substructure including information for each corresponding trial (in data.trial). Used trialinfo columns:

1. column: hemifield presentation during encoding (1 = left, 2 = right)
2. column: task condition (1 = encoding, 2 = voluntary retrieval, 3 = involuntary retrieval)
3. old or new item (1 – old; 0 – new)
4. visual discrimination task response
5. column: reaction time
6. column: responses
 - 212 – involuntary hit
 - 112 – voluntary hit
 - 211 – involuntary correct rejection
 - 111 – voluntary correct rejection
 - 202 – involuntary false alarm
 - 102 – voluntary false alarm
 - 201 – involuntary miss

 - 101 – voluntary miss
7. column: source memory response
 - 132 & 131 voluntary correct source memory
 - 122 & 121 voluntary wrong source memory

232 & 231 involuntary correct source memory

222 & 221 involuntary wrong source memory

8. column: item memory

153 & 154 voluntary correct item memory

143 & 144 voluntary wrong item memory

253 & 254 involuntary correct item memory

243 & 244 involuntary wrong item memory

9. item ID

10. column: memory performance

10 – voluntary hit; 11 - voluntary false alarm; 12 – voluntary correct rejection;
13 - voluntary miss

20 – involuntary hit; 21 - involuntary false alarm; 22 – involuntary correct
rejection; 23 - involuntary miss

11. column: source memory performance

14 – voluntary source hit left; 15 – voluntary source hit right; 16 – voluntary
source miss left; 17 – voluntary source miss right

24 – involuntary source hit left; 25 – involuntary source hit right; 26 –
involuntary source miss left; 27 – involuntary source miss right

12. column: item memory

18 – voluntary item hit; 19 – voluntary item miss

28 – involuntary item hit; 29 – involuntary item miss

13. column: full memory performance

31 – voluntary fullhit right; 32 voluntary fullhit left

41 – involuntary fullhit right; 42 involuntary fullhit left

14. column: voluntary retrieval performance for an item

encoding full hit left - 1
encoding full hit right - 2
retrieval full hit left - 3
retrieval full hit right - 4
encoding miss left - 5
encoding miss right - 6
retrieval miss left - 7
retrieval miss right - 8

15. column: involuntary retrieval performance for an item

encoding full hit left - 1

encoding full hit right - 2
retrieval full hit left - 3
retrieval full hit right - 4
encoding miss left - 5
encoding miss right - 6
retrieval miss left - 7
retrieval miss right - 8

03Sources\electrodes

Electrode positions of each subject in MNI space

Scripts

Scripts depend on outcomes of previous results. Please run scripts in the following order to replicate results.

a03behavioral.m

Behavioral analyses of data

a04_TF_analysis.m

Time-frequency analysis of preprocessed data.

a05b_source_DF.m.m

Source estimation of sensor data

a05d_source_TF_stats.m

Source analysis statistics and plots

a06a_RSA_Enc_perm.m

Representational similarity analysis of encoding data to identify time window of lateralized processing during encoding.

a06a_RSA_Topo_Enc_Perm.m.m

Representational similarity analysis of encoding data to identify electrodes representing information of the left or right hemifield. Significant electrodes of this analysis are used for further representational similarity analyses.

a06b_RSA_Retrieval_perm.m

Encoding-retrieval similarity analyses to test item-specific reinstatement during voluntary and involuntary retrieval.

a06d_RSA_Retrieval_contralat_elec_perm.m

Encoding-retrieval similarity analysis of visual field specific reactivation. Here, only electrodes identified with the script “a06a_RSA_Topo_Enc_Perm.m.m” are used.

a07ReactivationCompression.m

Reactivation compression analyses and comparison between voluntary and involuntary retrieval.

Matlab version:

All scripts were tested using Matlab 2017a and Windows 11.

Matlab toolboxes:

Fieldtrip Version fieldtrip-20170517
cbrewer toolbox

raincloud plot toolbox matlab